

Is women's work enough to reduce poverty in Vietnam? (A new approach to equivalence of scales using jointly model of labor supply and commodity demands)

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the role of women's work in reducing poverty in Vietnam during the period of 2004-08. We use t-test to compare the equality of means of a group of family with working woman and a group of family with non-working woman using two indexes to calculate expenditure per capita: (1) expenditure per capita; (2) expenditure per equivalence of scales. Expenditure per capita is simply counting the number of people in a household while expenditure per equivalence of scale deflates expenditure by the number of children scaling by some fractions of an adult. This is our contribution to the literature since no research has used expenditure per equivalence of scale before. The determinants of poverty rates in Vietnam are also considered. The result shows that women's work itself is not enough to reduce poverty in Vietnam. The problem of being poor mainly comes from other characteristics rather than women's work such as husband's wage, family's asset, the number of years of schooling of the husband, the number of years of schooling of the wife and the age of the wife.

JEL Classification: I3.

Keywords: (poverty, equivalence scale).

1. The facts: economic growths, poverty rates, and women's work in Vietnam

1.1 Economic growths and poverty rates

Vietnam has experienced a prolonged period of economic booming after the milestone policy called Doimoi in 1986. The economy is pulled by the two wheels of industry and services rather than agriculture after the Doimoi. Indeed, table 1 shows economic structure by industry. As can be seen, the agriculture dominates two other sectors in the economy before Doimoi in terms of the contribution to GDP. For example, the agriculture accounted for 47.6 percent of GDP in 1976, and hit for a number of 58.6 percent in 1982. Meanwhile, the industry and service both reduced their contribution gradually during the period of 1976-1982. In particular, industry and services sectors accounted for less than 50 percent of GDP in 1982. The data in panel B indicating the economy after Doimoi policy, however, give a different picture. The service has caught up agriculture in 1990. This year marked an equal proportion of agriculture and service in GDP. However, agriculture is left behind, while industry and service are the two emerging sectors in 2010.

Table 1: Economic structure by industry

	%				
Panel A: Before Doimoi	1976	1978	1980	1981	1982
Agriculture	47.6	46.9	54.3	56.6	58.6
Industry	33.9	33.2	24.7	26.3	30.0
Services	18.5	19.9	21.0	17.0	11.3
Panel B: After Doimoi	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010
Agriculture	38.7	27.2	24.5	21.0	20.6
Industry	22.7	28.8	36.7	41.0	41.1
Services	38.6	44.1	38.7	38.0	38.3

Sources: General Statistics Office

Along with economic growth, poverty has been reduced sharply during this time. The figures show that the poverty rate in 2010 was reduced to 14.2% from the number of 34.4 in 1995. Especially, the poverty rates are observed to reduce sharply during the period of 2004-2008: the poverty rate in 2004 was 18.1%; in 2006 was 15.5%; in 2008 was 13.4%. This downward trend of poverty rates is along with an upward trend of economic growth during the period of 2004-08. A question arising here is that whether or not economic growth will reduce poverty? And, what factor contributes to this reduction?

1.2 The pattern of Vietnamese female workers

The Vietnamese female labor plays an important role in the whole economy in general and in the labor market in particular. The proportion of female labor force in the population of working age is very large. Table 2 shows the labor force at 15 years old or above by sex. As can be seen, the total labor force of Vietnam raises 30.7 percent, of which male increase by 32.5 percent and female increases by 28.9 percent. In 2010, total labor force of Vietnam is 50.4 million people, of which male is 25.9 million people and female is 24.5 million people. Looking at the structure of the labor force, we see that female labor accounts for a relatively high rate. Indeed, the share of male labor was 50.7 percent, while it was 49.3 percent for female labor in 2000. Although the number of female in the labor force reduces slightly, but remains a high proportion of the total in 2010. For instance, male labor accounts for 51.4 percent and female labor accounts for 48.6 percent.

Table 2: Structure of labor force at 15 years old or above by sex

Year	Total	%	
		Male	Female
2000	100.0	50.7	49.3
2001	100.0	51.0	49.0
2002	100.0	50.9	49.1
2003	100.0	51.3	48.7
2004	100.0	51.0	49.0
2005	100.0	52.3	47.7
2006	100.0	53.2	46.8
2007	100.0	50.8	49.2
2008	100.0	51.3	48.7
2009	100.0	52.0	48.0
2010	100.0	51.4	48.6

Source: General Statistics Office

The distribution of female workers is a good index in telling us about what sector is female-intensive. From the data on the Vietnam Household Living Standard Survey 2010, we calculate the distribution of female workers in 7 sectors. The result shows that agriculture and manufacturing are the sectors have the most frequent among 7 sectors. Following is transportation, other services, construction, electricity, water supply, and mining.

Table 3 presents the distribution of working days per month of the first job of female by age. As can be seen, distribution of working days per month is very different by age groups between sectors. Surprisingly, distribution of female workers aged 10-22 in agriculture is the highest group among age groups. This means that females start working at a very early age in agriculture. We have seen a number of 34.3 percent of females aged 10-15 and of 33.1 percent of females aged 16-22 in agriculture. Females aged 23-26 dominate in mining and manufacturing sectors. Meanwhile, the sectors of electricity, water supply and construction show the biggest rates among group aged 16-26. Conversely, transportation and other services have the distributions of the highest rates of the group aged 23-30.

Table 3: Distribution of working days per month of first job of female by age %

Working Days	Agriculture	Mining	Manufacturing	Electricity & Water Supply	Construction	Transport services	Services
<10	9.8	0.0	1.5	0.0	3.0	0.7	1.7
10-15	34.3	4.3	7.1	3.7	17.0	6.3	5.1
16-22	33.1	17.4	17.8	40.7	32.6	15.8	16.3
23-26	16.4	65.2	58.8	29.6	40.7	44.9	45.5
27-30	6.4	13.0	14.8	25.9	6.7	32.4	31.5
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Author's calculation

Vietnam has a relatively high female participation rate as compared to other Asian countries. Table 4 shows the female participation rate by country from 2000 to 2010. As can be seen, three countries in Indochina peninsula have the highest participation rates as compared to other Asian countries. During this period, although the female participation rates in these three countries have gone down, but they still stay at the high rates. Among three, Laos has the highest rate with 80 percent, followed by Cambodia (78 percent), and Vietnam (75 percent) in 1993. However, the situation has changed since 2011. Cambodia becomes the country having the highest rate, followed by Laos and Vietnam. Similarly, other countries such as China and Thailand has the relatively high female participation, but at different rates, except the Philippines. Moreover, the female participation rate in each country has the different trend during the period 1993-2011. The female participation rate in Thailand is quite stable during this period. The number is around 63-67 percent. Meanwhile, it decreases gradually in China from 73 percent in 1993 to 68 percent in 2011. It is decided to consider female participation rate by age group. This will helps us to have a clearer cut of picture of Vietnam female labor.

Table 4. Female participation rate by country %

	Vietnam	Laos	Cambodia	Thailand	Philippines	China
2000	74	79	77	65	49	71
2001	74	79	76	65	53	71
2002	74	79	76	65	52	70
2003	74	78	76	65	51	70
2004	74	78	75	65	50	70
2005	74	78	76	66	50	69
2006	73	78	78	65	49	69
2007	73	77	79	65	48	69
2008	73	77	79	65	49	68
2009	73	77	79	63	49	68
2010	73	77	79	64	50	68

Source: The World Bank

Figure 1 depicts the female participation rate in Vietnam by age groups. As can be seen, there is an

inverted U-shaped relationship between the female participation rate and the female's age in Vietnam. The participation rate of the group aged 20-24 or below is unstable, particularly within the group aged 15-19. Indeed, the participation rate of the group aged 15-19 decreased sharply, and the group aged 20-24 went down gradually from 1993 to 2008. Moreover, the participation rate of the group aged 25-54 is stable at a relatively high rate. However, the group aged 55 or above had a downward trend as compared to the group aged 25-54, but it has not fluctuated over time.

Figure 2 shows married female participation rate in Vietnam during the period 1993-2008. As can be seen, we do not observe an inverted U-shaped of the married female participation rate. Instead, we find a stable single line in the group aged 15-54. The participation rate of the group aged 55 or above tends to fall down sharply as we have seen in figure 1. This figure also reveals that the participation rate of the married female aged 15-54 were about 80 percent or higher. This number is much higher than that of the overall participation rate.

Figure 3 shows the single female participation rate in Vietnam. As can be seen, there co-exists M-shaped and inverted U-shaped in this figure. For example, we observe an M-shaped relationship between the single female participation rate and the female's age in 1993.

However, it indicates an inverted U-shaped in other years. Furthermore, it is very difficult to talk about the trend of the single participation rate in Vietnam during this period due to the sharp fluctuations, particularly in the group aged 15-24 and the group aged 55 or above.

2. Statement of the problem

2.1 Why women's work is one of important factors in reducing poverty rate?

From theoretical point of view, unemployment and underemployment lies at the core of poverty. For the poor, labor is often the only asset they can use to improve their well-being. Hence the creation of productive employment opportunities is essential for achieving poverty reduction and sustainable economic and social development. It is crucial to provide decent jobs that both secure income and empowerment of the poor, especially women and younger people.

Rapid economic growth can potentially bring a high rate of expansion of productive and remunerative employment, which can lead to a reduction in poverty. Nevertheless, the contribution of the growth process to poverty reduction does not depend only on the rate of economic growth, but also on the ability of the poor to respond to the increasing demand for labor in most product categories of employment. Given the importance of employment for poverty reduction, job-creation should occupy a central place in national poverty reduction strategies. Many employment strategies are often related to agricultural and rural development and include using labor-intensive agricultural technologies; developing small and medium-size enterprises, and promoting micro projects in rural areas. Many strategies promote self-employment, non-farm employment in rural areas, targeted employment interventions, microfinance and credit as a means of employment generation, skill formation and training. Such strategies, however, often address the quantity of employment while the qualitative dimensions, such as equity, security, dignity and freedom are often absent or minimal.

2.2 Lack of methods of measuring women's work in poverty reduction in Vietnam

There is a large number of studies relating to the matter of poverty in Vietnam. Among them, the study on the relationship between trade liberalization and poverty is of interest to many researchers. Jenkins (2003) examines the impact of trade flows on employment and poverty in Vietnam since the early 1990s. The outcome indicates that the increase of export has had a significantly positive effect on employment, while the increase in import competition had a negative effect both directly and indirectly through rationalization of producers facing foreign competition. Justino et al. (2008) investigates the transmission mechanism between trade policy reform

and the household welfare outcomes. They find that trade liberalization has a positive force on rural household welfare and is largely transmitted to the poor through the labor marketplace. Niimi et al. (2007) study the influence of the trade liberalization on poverty in Vietnam over the 1990s. They find that trade liberalization could change the household poverty status. In addition, trade effects will enable us to experience a priori who are better off and worse off.

Trade liberalization also reduces poverty over the period of 1993-98. Heo and Nguyen (2009) find that trade liberalization has increased the growth of the economy, therefore passing to a higher GDP per capita and a lower poverty rate. It also brings benefits to the poor through creating pro-poor employment and growing wages. Another impact on income and substitution effects is that it lowers domestic prices of importable goods and increases domestic prices of exportable goods such as rice and coffee. In addition, it has indirectly benefited to the poor through the higher government revenues, which result in raising subsidy to the poor. However, the negative impact is that it increases the gap between urban and rural areas.

The topics such as the effect of rice prices, microfinance and foreign remittance on poverty are of interest of many researchers as well. Accordingly, Ut et al. (2001) investigate the impact of modern farm technology and infrastructure in income distribution and poverty in Vietnam. They find that the adoption of modern rice varieties under irrigated conditions increases rice yield and reduces unit cost of rice production, but the profit and income effect are insignificant when cultivating under rain field conditions. Poverty is lower in the developed villages than those of the less developed ones. Along with this finding, Niimi et al. (2004) find that the higher rice production in Vietnam are of a result of reforms which contributes to the poverty reduction. Furthermore, Minot et al. (1998) suggest that although export liberalization of rice could raise food prices and increase regional inequality, it could also increase average real income and reduce the incidence and severity poverty.

Bali et al. (2008) believe that microfinance has a positive impact on the livelihood of the poor through accumulation of social, human, financial, natural and physical assets. Indeed, they find that the process of accumulation of assets, thus leading to creation of livelihood will increase the household income and reduce poverty. Nguyen (2008) examines the impact of the governmental micro credit program for the poor on poverty reduction. He finds that the program is important in terms of poverty targeting. The non-poor account for a larger proportion of participants in the program. The non-poor also tend to receive the larger amounts of credits as compared to the poor. However, the program has decreased the poverty rate of the participants. Nguyen (2008) finds that receiving foreign remittances increases household income and consumption apparently, but it decreases poverty of the remittance recipients slightly.

The subjects of welfare comparison, inequality and poverty are also of interest to many researchers. For example, Liu (2001) studies the impact of market reform on inequality and poverty in Vietnam during the 1990s. She finds that on overall, inequality increases slightly not only between urban and rural areas but also between regions. The market reforms also decrease poverty which makes Vietnam becoming one of the best performers among developing countries. However, poverty reduction in rural area is found to be sluggish than that of urban areas. Meanwhile, Justino et al. (2004) examine welfare in Vietnam during the 1990s with particular concerns on poverty, inequality and poverty dynamics. They find that regardless of the level of the poverty line, poverty in Vietnam falls from 1992 to 1998. All the same, it is sensitive to the choice of the poverty line. Poverty is accompanied by an increasing inequality. The regional differences are important and the shifts in employment and production patterns are significantly connected to the alterations in living standards over time. White et al. (2003) claim that when calculating income-poverty profile, it is necessary to adjust by the household size and composition. If the adjustments are not made, the rural poverty is under-stated, particularly the groups of minority ethnic and female headed households. Nguyen (2011) forecasts whether or not Vietnam can achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). He finds that Vietnam may be able to achieve its MDGs on reduction the overall poverty, but not food poverty.

Minot (2000) exemplifies a method for generating disaggregated poverty maps. He finds that poverty in Vietnam is concentrated in the north and in the farthest districts from the coast and urban centers. Imai et al. (2011) measure poverty, inequality and ethnic minorities in Vietnam. Their analysis confirms that the

households belong to the ethnic minority groups are not only poorer but also more vulnerable to various shocks than those of majority groups. The household composition, training, land holding and location are the significant determinants of consumption and poverty. Moreover, the returns to the characteristics of the minority groups such as educational attainment or location are much more modest than those of the majority groups.

We can list some other studies such as Brauw et al. (2006) use panel data to see whether the households in Vietnam use seasonal migration to increase their living standards during the 1990s. He finds that about 5.2 percentage point of the annual expenditure growth to increase migration. Migration accounts for about 3 percentage point in decreasing poverty headcount ratio. In their research, Giang et al. (2009) examine the likely use of the social pension scheme in reducing poverty of the elderly in Vietnam. They notice that depending on the characteristics of the social pension, there would be beneficial poverty reductions. The targeting the elderly in rural areas are the most effective utilization of the limited resources. Combining the lower benefits with the lower eligibility requirements is more effective at reducing poverty than providing the larger benefits to a more limited group of receivers. Mont et al. (2011) find that disability is significantly correlated with poverty in Vietnam.

Indeed, we have found many studies on the issues of poverty, such as poverty determinants, poverty dominance and others. However, we think that such research has not covered adequately all problems of poverty, especially the issues of poverty in Vietnam for a number of reasons. Firstly, although the causal factors of poverty are investigated in many countries and country groups, but the important factors of poverty in Vietnam are still equivocal. Secondly, most researchers look at the poverty dominance of two or more distributions over time or by regional differences. There is no one who considers the connection of work and poverty, particularly the poverty between groups of working women and non-working women. Our research will be the first one which considers carefully this matter.

3. Methodology

We will first apply t-test to test the equality of means of the two groups to know which group has the highest poverty rates. For a broad understanding about poverty in Vietnam, we will appear into the determinants of the poverty rates.

In our research, we will use two expenditure indexes (1) expenditure per capita and (2) expenditure per equivalence capita. The former will count the number of people in a household while the latter will deflate the number of children by some fractions of adults. We will compare how poverty rates are different if we use different indicators.

Browning (1992) sums up various ways to calculate adult equivalence scales in the literature. The oldest method is called the Engel's method which has been applied by Watts (1967), Espenshade (1984), Deaton and Muellbauer (1986). Another famous method is the Rorthbarth method (see Rothbarth 1943, Deaton and Muellbauer 1986). The utility, based methods are first discussed in Muellbauer (1974) and later have been used by many researchers.

One of the advantages of the utility methods is that it is easy to include many factors in the familiar consumer behavior theory. For example, we can append the time costs of children into the literature on the costs of children. Another advantage is that the utility based methods are built under a plausible assumption as compared to the Engel or Rorthbarth methods. Furthermore, by estimating demand system, we will not just deliver the results on equivalence scale, but also integrate back to the indirect utility which corresponds to the consumers' preferences.

In this paper, we will use the equivalence of scales which are derived from Nghiem (2016). In her paper, Nghiem has proposed a revised AIDS Kooreman and Kapteyn (1985) model by adding savings variable as a new variable and extending the age of children into 3 groups to measure its effect on female labor supply. This model enables us to get equivalence of scales from the jointly model of labor supply and commodity demands. Equivalence of scales using jointly model is different from one derived from demand system in the literature in a way: jointly model considers not only expenditures but also income and savings behavior, while original consumer demand system only considers from consumer demand side. This is new in the literature, since no other researchers have applied such method to calculate equivalence of scales.

We will compare poverty dominances of the following two distributions by: employment status of the wife;

group of family with working wife for each of the periods 2004 and 2008; group of family with nonworking wife for each of the periods 2004 and 2008; by educational level of the wife; by headship of the family (male headed or female headed); by type of employment of the working wife; by family size; the determinants of poverty will tell us how much the difference in characteristics between groups affecting the probability of being poor of the family.

Probit function of the determinants of poverty will be assumed under the form of

$$P = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \dots + \alpha_n X_n + \varepsilon$$

where P is probability of being poor of the family; $X_1, X_2 \dots X_n$ are the determinants of poverty such as the number of persons in family, values of assets, husband's wage, the number of years of schooling of the husband, the number of years of schooling of the wife, the age of the wife.

4. Empirical Results

Table 5 shows the comparisons of poverty rates by working status of the wife in urban areas. As can be seen, poverty rates vary differently by the different working status of the wife. Looking at the results of 4 indexes in the period 2004-08, poverty rate of family with non-working wife is higher than that of the one with a working wife in 2008 for per equivalent adjusted index. The poverty rate of group with working wife is not lower than that of the one with non-working wife. This means that working status does not bring families out of poverty in urban areas.

Educational level and employment industry of the wife make poverty rates of two groups differently. Indeed, 3 over 4 poverty rates of family with a low-educated wife is higher than that of a family with high-educated wife; poverty rates of a family with the wife working in agriculture are higher than that of one working in industry and service. Other factors such as the family's headship, the family's size, and wage of the wife do not reduce poverty greatly. For example, 3 poverty rates of the family with the wife's headed are equal to the ones of the family with the husband's headed. The big-size family is found to have the same poverty rate with the small-size family.

Table 5: Comparisons of poverty rates by the wife's working status in urban areas

		Poverty comparisons	
		Using expenditure per capita	Using expenditure per equivalent of scale
By wife's working status			
2004	Poverty non-work = Poverty work	Poverty non-work = Poverty work	
2008	Poverty non-work = Poverty work	Poverty non-work > Poverty work	
By wife's education			
2004	Poverty low_educated > Poverty high_educated	Poverty low_educated = Poverty high_educated	
2008	Poverty low_educated > Poverty high_educated	Poverty low_educated > Poverty high_educated	
By family's headship			
2004	Poverty non-headed > Poverty headed	Poverty non-headed = Poverty headed	
2008	Poverty non-headed = Poverty headed	Poverty non-headed = Poverty headed	
By industry			
2004	Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry	Poverty agriculture = Poverty Industry	
2008	Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry	Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry	
By family's size			
2004	Poverty big size > Poverty small size	Poverty big size = Poverty small size	
2008	Poverty big size = Poverty small size	Poverty big size = Poverty small size	
By wife's wage level			
2004	Poverty low wage = Poverty high wage	Poverty low wage = Poverty high wage	
2008	Poverty low wage < Poverty high wage	Poverty low wage = Poverty high wage	

Table 6 gives the comparisons of poverty rates by working status of the wife in rural area. As can be

seen, factors such as working status, educational levels, headship status, industry, family size and wage level of the wife have different effects on poverty rates in rural area. Poverty rates calculating from consumption per capita index and consumption per equivalent adjusted index give the different results as well. When using consumption per capita index, working status of the wife does not reduce poverty rate of the family with working wife. However, when using consumption per equivalent adjusted index, family with non-working wife is lower than that of poverty with working wife.

Table 6: Comparisons of poverty rates by working status of the wife in rural areas

		Poverty comparisons by	
		Using expenditure per capita	Using expenditure per equivalent of scale
By wife's working status			
2004	Poverty non-work = Poverty work		Poverty non-work < Poverty work
2008	Poverty non-work = Poverty work		Poverty non-work < Poverty work
By wife's education			
2004	Poverty low_educated > Poverty high_educated		Poverty low_educated = Poverty high_educated
2008	Poverty low_educated > Poverty high_educated		Poverty low_educated = Poverty high_educated
By family's headship			
2004	Poverty non-headed > Poverty headed		Poverty non-headed > Poverty headed
2008	Poverty non-headed > Poverty headed		Poverty non-headed > Poverty headed
By industry			
2004	Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry		Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry
2008	Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry		Poverty agriculture > Poverty Industry
By family's size			
2004	Poverty big size > Poverty small size		Poverty big size = Poverty small size
2008	Poverty big size > Poverty small size		Poverty big size = Poverty small size
By wife's wage level			
2004	Poverty low wage > Poverty high wage		Poverty low wage = Poverty high wage
2008	Poverty low wage > Poverty high wage		Poverty low wage = Poverty high wage

Factors including educational level, family size and wage level give the opposite results between the two consumption per capita indexes. Family with low-educated wife has a higher poverty rate than that of family with high-educated wife for consumption per capital index. In contrast, family with low-educated wife has an equal poverty rate with family with high-educated wife for consumption per capital index. Family size and wage level show the similar trends with the factor of educational level of the wife.

Family headship and employment industry of the wife give the same results in the two indexes. For example, a family with the wife's headed is less pure than that of families with the husband's headed; family with the wife working in agriculture sector is poorer than that of family with the wife working in

industry and service sectors.

We will talk about the causal factors of poverty rate by working status of the married woman using Probit model. The causal factors of poverty rate by other factors are awarded in the Appendix due to the lack of space. Table 7 indicates the determinants of poverty rate of family with a working wife. This table will yield us an understanding of the signboards of the causal factors. As can be seen, all parameters have negative signs, except the parameter number of persons. This suggests that a number of persons have a positive effect on poverty, while other factors reduce it. Family with asset and high wage of husband will have a low poverty rate. Number of years of schooling of husband and wife and the age of the wife will decrease poverty. The wage of a husband has the biggest effect on reducing poverty rate; followed by family's asset, number of schooling of husband, number of schooling of wife and the age of wife.

Table 7: The determinants of poverty rate of a family with a working wife in urban areas

Poverty rate in urban areas	Coefficients	Standard Errors	t	p-value	95% Confident Interval	
Number of persons in family	0.244	0.124	1.97	0.049	0.001	0.487
Log-asset of family	-0.214	0.074	-2.90	0.004	-0.358	-0.069
Number of years of schooling of the wife	-0.044	0.041	-1.07	0.284	-0.123	0.036
Age of the wife	-0.038	0.021	-1.80	0.072	-0.078	0.003
Number of years of schooling of husband	-0.049	0.038	-1.28	0.199	-0.124	0.026
Log-wage of husband	-0.610	0.202	-3.03	0.002	-1.007	-0.216
Constant term	6.530	2.270	2.88	0.004	2.083	10.980
Number of observations :565	Prob. > Chi2: 0.000					
LR Chi2 (6): 46.33	Pseudo R2: 0.35					

Table 8 shows the determinants of poverty rate of family with non-working wife. As can be seen, all variables show the similar effects with the ones in table 7. That is, family's asset and wage of husband have a negative effect on poverty rate of family with a non-working wife; the number of persons has a positive effect. Family's asset has the higher effect than that of wage of husband in terms of reducing poverty rate of family with a non-working wife.

Table 8: The determinants of poverty rate of a family with a non-working wife in urban areas

Poverty rate in urban areas	Coefficients	Standard Errors	t	p-value	95% Confident Interval	
Number of persons in family	0.211	0.141	1.49	0.136	-0.066	0.487
Log-asset of family	-0.233	0.122	-1.90	0.057	-0.473	0.007
Log-wage of husband	-0.697	0.297	-2.35	0.019	-1.280	-0.115
Constant term	5.682	3.358	1.69	0.091	-0.899	12.264
Number of observations: 113	Prob. > Chi2: 0.0012					
LR Chi2 (6): 15.89	Pseudo R2: 0.388					

The determinants of poverty rate of a family with a working wife in rural areas are a little bit different from one in urban areas. Table 9 shows the determinants of poverty rate of a family with a working wife in rural areas. As can be seen, six predictors are statistically significant at 5 percent confident interval: number of

persons in family, log-asset of family, the age of the wife, number of years of schooling of the husband, log-wage of husband, and constant term. Only predictor, number of years of schooling of the wife is not statistically significant. Among them, number of persons in family has a positive effect on probability of being poor. Other factors have a negative effect.

**Table 9: The determinants of poverty rate of a family
With a working wife in rural areas**

Poverty rate in rural areas	Coefficients	Standard Errors	t	p- value	95% Confident Interval	
Number of persons in family	0.242	0.042	5.80	0.000	0.160	0.323
Log-asset of family	-0.078	0.031	-2.50	0.012	-0.139	-0.167
Number of years of schooling of the wife	-0.030	0.019	-1.59	0.113	-0.067	0.007
The age of the wife	-0.017	0.008	-2.14	0.032	-0.033	-0.002
Number of years of schooling of the husband	-0.037	0.018	-2.10	0.036	-0.072	-0.003
Log-wage of husband	-0.432	0.090	-4.81	0.000	-0.610	-0.256
Constant term	2.954	0.945	3.12	0.002	1.101	4.807
Number of observations: 1205	Prob. > Chi2: 0.000					
LR Chi2 (6): 92.30	Pseudo R2: 0.164					

The factors such as number of persons in family, log-asset of family, log-wage of husband are the most important determinants of poverty rate of a family with a non-working wife in rural areas. Table 10 shows the result of estimation of Probit model for rural areas. As can be seen, all of these predictors are not statistically significant. However, we need to keep this estimation to see the sign of all predictors for reference. We can say that, similar to family with working wife in rural areas, number of persons in family also has a positive effect on probability of being poor; other factors have a negative effect with the largest magnitude is log-wage of husband, followed by log-assets of family.

**Table 10: The determinants of poverty rate of a family
with a non-working wife in rural areas**

Poverty rate in rural areas	Coefficients	Standard Errors	t	p- value	95% Confident Interval	
Number of persons in family	0.048	0.183	0.26	0.793	-0.311	0.407
Log-asset of family	-0.036	0.110	-0.33	0.745	-0.251	0.180
Log-wage of husband	-0.800	0.379	-2.11	0.035	-1.542	-0.058
Constant term	6.072	3.888	1.56	0.118	-1.549	13.692
Number of observations: 62	Prob. > Chi2: 0.11					
LR Chi2 (6): 5.90	Pseudo R2: 0.17					

5. Conclusion

The result in table 5 and 6 shows that a family with working wife equally poor as a family with non-working wife in both urban and rural areas regardless of using any poverty index. Moreover, the facts also indicate that poverty rate increase from 2004 to 2008. This may be ascribable to the issue of high inflation during this period.

Besides, a family with a highly educated working wife is less poor that that of a family with a low educated working wife in both urban and rural areas. A family with a male headed is less poor than that of a family with a female headed if the family is in urban areas. However, we reject the null hypothesis 5 if the family belongs to

rural areas. This interesting result may reveal that female headed family manages their consumption better than that of a male headed family in rural areas. A family with wife working in industry or service sectors is less poor than that of a family with wife working in agriculture sector in both urban and rural areas. It is true that industry and service sectors give the higher earnings than that of agriculture sector. The higher earnings bring the families to be further from the poverty lines. A small size family is less poor than that of a big size one. It is reasonable that the more people the more consumption demands. However, the more demand facing the limited budget consumption means the more probability of being poor. A family with the higher wage of the wife is less poor than that of a family with the lower wife's wage.

The causal factors of poverty are the number of persons in the family, value of assets, husband's wages and, the number of years of schooling of the husband, the number of years of schooling of the wife, and age of the wife. These causal factors have different effects on poverty rate in Vietnam. For the family with a working wife, husband's wages has the biggest effect in reducing poverty rate; followed by family's assets, the number of years of schooling of husband, the number of years of schooling of wife, and the age of wife. For the family with a non-working wife, family's asset has the largest effect in reducing poverty rate.

In our research we try to employ the expenditure per equivalence adjusted for poverty analysis. We find that these two indexes give the consistent results. However, they give the opposite outcomes when we consider poverty by year. For example, using expenditure per capita index, almost indicators affirm that poverty rates in 2008 are larger than those of ones in 2004. Meanwhile, poverty rates of family with a working wife, or one with a male headed, or others in 2008 are equal with those in 2004. These results suggest that we should measure poverty rate by many indexes to get the rational conclusion. Nevertheless, we could face a potential problem of bias. The judgment of a choice of indexes is out of the scope and it leaves for the further research in this matter.

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